

GENERATING DESIGN ALLOWABLE FROM SMOOTH SPECIMENS

P. D. Shah¹, J. D. D. Melo² and C. A. Cimini Jr.³

¹Research Associate ²Visiting Scholar

Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics / Stanford University
Durand Building, 496 Lomita Mall, Stanford, CA, U.S.A., 94305-4035

¹pdshah@stanford.edu ²dmelo@stanford.edu

³Associate Professor

Center for Aeronautical Studies / Department of Mechanical Engineering

Federal University of Minas Gerais

Av. Antônio Carlos 6627, Belo Horizonte, MG, Brazil, 312790-901

³cimini@ufmg.br

SUMMARY

In this work, numerical models were applied to investigate the effects of notches and loading conditions on the strength of smooth laminates. Results from simulation showed that loading conditions play a significant role on strength of notched laminates and failure cannot be predicted based only on uniaxial tensile and compressive strength.

Keywords: design allowable; notched specimens; smooth specimens; data

INTRODUCTION

There has been a steady increase in the use of composites in the aircraft industry over the past few years. Besides the well known weight savings which has direct implications in fuel efficiency, the additional benefits include reduced maintenance and a higher passenger comfort level. Therefore, a continuing trend of increase in the use of composites for aircraft structures is expected at present and in the future.

Aircraft structures contain many holes and notches due to the presence of windows, doors and also for bolted joints. The development of stress concentrations due to the notches is always of a great concern. As a result, many studies have been conducted to investigate notched fiber reinforced laminates [1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15]. These studies have considered a variety of notch geometries to assess notched strength including center notch [1,2,3,4], double edge notches [3,5,6], open holes and filled holes [3,4,7,8,9,10,12,13,14,15].

A common practice of aircraft designers is the use of notched specimens to generate design allowable. Among all geometries studied, open hole and filled hole tests have been adopted as industry standards [16,17,18,19]. In addition to generating design allowable for notched structures, open hole strength data is sometimes considered as a knockdown factor on laminate strength to account for manufacturing defects and impact damage. The experimental program to generate such data sets may cost up to 20 million dollars and two years of work [20]. Yet, in spite of the very high cost and time required, the experimental data obtained from these tests provide information which is only

specific to the tested conditions. This is because the trends obtained from notched specimens are very much dependent upon variables such as material properties, ply orientation and stacking sequence, geometric factors (laminates thickness and notch size), and loading conditions (uniaxial, biaxial or more complex systems). Therefore, the experimental data will be useful only for the tested conditions and any change would require a new testing program. This drawback limits designers in exploring the full potential of composite materials due to the cost and time involved in generating new design data. Thus, traditionally, the design paradigm does not explore beyond the realm of $[\pi/4]$ quasi-isotropic laminates known as "black aluminum", which does not take full advantage of anisotropy. Moreover, since the design data obtained from notched specimens is highly dependent upon loading conditions, test results should not be directly applied to the design of structures, which are normally subjected to states of stress much more complex than simple uniaxial tension or compression.

In this work, numerical simulations using FEA (Finite Element Analysis) were used to predict strength properties of notched specimens based on ply properties from unnotched (smooth) specimens. The numerical model was used to investigate open hole and oblong slot strength of laminates under biaxial load conditions. First ply failure (FPF) and Last Ply Failure envelopes for Open Hole (OH) and also Oblong Slot (OS) specimens are compared to Tresca and Maximum Stress failure criteria. It should be noted that the Tresca and Maximum Stress failure envelopes are obtained using the anchor points based on uniaxial tension and compression data. Ultimate failure stress envelopes (maximum of FPF and LPF) for both types of notched specimens are also compared to those of smooth (unnotched) specimens. The effects of loading conditions (uniaxial and biaxial) on notched strength are studied and discussed.

The properties of smooth specimens used in this study are ply based. Ultimately, the long term goal is to be able to predict notched design allowable from constituent level properties using micromechanics of failure theory [21] and progressive damage models. In this case, fewer specimens can be used to validate the predictions and this furthers the reduction in cost and time involved.

METHODOLOGY

In order to investigate the influence of the notches (open hole and oblong slot) on the biaxial strength of composite laminates, the computational tool MicMac/FEA was used. This is a hybrid tool that associates the point design analysis of MicMac to a finite element analysis code which evaluates the points of stress concentration. Therefore, a point design analysis is performed in the points of maximum stress in the domain. The strength of the specimen, thus, was evaluated at the points of maximum stress for First Ply Failure (FPF) and Last Ply Failure (LPF) using the Tsai-Wu failure criterion. Last Ply Failure (LPF) analysis was performed using the simultaneous degradation scheme for all plies, where a degradation factor of 4% is used. Numerical models were developed considering the geometry for both notched specimens depicted in Figure 1. Note that the longitudinal size of the oblong slot has the same size of the hole diameter (0.01 m) for comparison.

Figure 1 – Geometry of the studied notched specimens.

The material system IM6/epoxy with ply thickness of 0.125 mm and the quasi-isotropic layup $[0/90/45/-45]_s$, standard in the industry, were selected. The ply based material properties are shown in Table 1. The finite element meshes for both notched specimens are shown in Figure 2. ABAQUS was the finite element analysis platform of choice for this study. The 4-node conventional shell element S4R with 6 degrees-of-freedom per node was selected. Boundary conditions were imposed in such a way that the biaxial loading could be applied to the developed models. Four load cases were evaluated for each model, corresponding to the four quadrants of the 2D σ_1 - σ_2 domain (tension-tension, compression-tension, compression-compression, and tension-compression).

Table 1 – IM6/epoxy material properties.

Property	Value
E_{11}	203 GPa
E_{22}	11.2 GPa
G_{12}	8.4 GPa
ν_{12}	0.32
X	3500 MPa
X'	1540 MPa
Y	56 MPa
Y'	150 MPa
S	98 MPa

Figure 2 – Finite element mesh used for the notched specimens.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to investigate the influence of the notches (open hole and oblong slot), results were presented as 2D failure envelopes in the σ_1 - σ_2 domain. Figure 3 shows the failure envelope for the smooth specimen. Note that the matrix intact area, controlled by FPF, and degraded matrix area, controlled by LPF, are respectively marked in blue and red.

Figure 3 –Failure envelope of smooth specimens for Tsai-Wu LPF (Last Ply Failure) criterion. Note the regions for intact matrix, in blue, and degraded matrix, in red.

The biaxial stress results for open hole specimens are shown in Figure 4, for Tsai-Wu's FPF and LPF criteria. Also shown are the failure envelopes for Tresca and Maximum Stress failure criteria for comparison. It can be seen that Tresca and Maximum Stress criteria clearly can not be applied. In the 1st and 3rd quadrants, Maximum Stress criterion is conservative and in the 2nd and 4th quadrants it is not conservative, while Tresca failure criterion is conservative in all quadrants.

Figure 4 – Open Hole specimen failure envelopes for FPF (First Ply Failure), in blue, and LPF (Last Ply Failure), in red, compared to Tresca and Maximum Stress failure criteria.

Figure 5 shows the failure envelope for open hole specimens, combining the FPF and LPF envelopes depicted in Figure 4. Also in Figure 5 there is a comparison among the smooth specimen and the open hole specimen failure envelopes. It can be observed the dramatic knockdown in strength the open hole introduces into a smooth laminate.

In Figure 6 it is presented the Safety Factor from the calculated results of Figure 5. The Safety Factor is defined as the ratio of the smooth specimen strength with respect to the notched specimen strength. The values for the Safety Factor vary from 2 to 4 depending on the biaxial stress ratios. Thus, measured data of Open Hole Tension (OHT) and Open Hole Compression (OHC), respectively shown as blue and green dots in Figure 6, having safety values around 2.5 can not predict how laminates with hole will behave under biaxial stresses. Therefore, uniaxial open hole test data will not provide a consistent safety to design a laminate and can be either over or under design. If a laminate must tolerate holes (for bolted repair, for instance) it should be designed using the Finite Element Analysis that includes holes at critical locations in the laminate.

Figure 5 – Open Hole specimen failure ultimate envelope (FPF+LPF), in black, and smooth specimen, in red.

Figure 6 – Distribution of Safety Factor (in red) with load definition for an open hole specimen (OHT – Open Hole Tension; OHC – Open Hole Compression).

The same kind of results is presented in Figure 7, this time for oblong slotted specimens. Failure envelopes for Tsai-Wu's FPF and LPF criteria and for Tresca and Maximum Stress failure criteria are shown. Again, Maximum Stress failure criterion is conservative in the 1st and 3rd quadrants and not conservative in the 2nd and 4th quadrants, while Tresca failure criterion is conservative in all quadrants.

Figure 7 – Oblong Slot specimen failure envelopes for FPF (First Ply Failure), in blue, and LPF (Last Ply Failure), in red, compared to Tresca and Maximum Stress failure criteria.

Figure 8 shows the failure envelope for oblong slotted specimens, combining the FPF and LPF envelopes depicted in Figure 7. The comparison among the smooth specimen and the oblong slotted specimen failure envelopes again shows the significant decrease in strength for oblong slotted specimens compared to the smooth laminate.

The summary of the effect of notches on the smooth laminates can be seen in Figure 9, which shows the failure envelopes for the smooth, open hole and oblong slotted specimens. The reduction in the failure strength due to the introduction of notches in an otherwise unnotched laminate is outstanding. There is no relation between uniaxial tensile and compressive strengths at the anchor points where failure envelope crosses the coordinate axes. It is also interesting to note that a simple knockdown factor to account for the loss of strength due to the notches will not work. Each notch under each biaxial loading will have to be calculated.

This further reinforces the fact that test results obtained from uniaxial tests for notched specimens are indeed very much specific to that particular case and should not be relied upon to develop design data sets. However, with one set of ply data from smooth specimens, one can effectively predict the strength of both notched and unnotched samples. This significantly reduces the cost and time involved for such predictions.

Figure 8 – Oblong Slot specimen failure ultimate envelope (FPF+LPF), in black, and smooth specimen, in red.

Figure 9 – Comparison among smooth, in red, and notched (Open Hole, in black, and Oblong Slot, in green) specimens failure ultimate envelopes.

CONCLUSIONS

A numerical analysis using MicMac/FEA was performed to predict strength properties of notched specimens based on ply properties from unnotched (smooth) specimens.

Results showed that effects of loading conditions (uniaxial and biaxial) on notched strength are dramatic, with Safety Factors that could reach the value of 4 for the studied geometry, layup and material. There is no relation between uniaxial tensile and compressive strengths at the anchor points. Also, it can be noted that a simple knockdown factor for strength loss will not work. In other words, there is the need to calculate the Safety Factor for each notch under each biaxial loading. Therefore, uniaxial open hole test data is not enough to provide a consistent safe design. These test results are specific to that particular case and should not be relied upon for the whole biaxial load domain. However, it is possible to predict the strength of both notched and unnotched samples from one set of ply data from smooth specimens. This should be done in order to reduce the cost and time involved in the process of obtaining the design allowable.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

CAPES Brasilia/Brazil is acknowledged for the fellowship support of the authors José Daniel D. Melo and Carlos A. Cimini Jr.

References

1. Coats T.W. and Harris, C.E (1999). A Progressive Damage Methodology for Residual Strength Predictions of Notched Composite Panels, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **33**(23):2193–224.
2. Dimant, R.A., Shercliff, H.R. and Beaumont, P.W.R. (2002). Evaluation of a Damage-Mechanics Approach to the Modeling of Notched Strength in KFRP and GRP Cross-Ply Laminates, *Composites Science and Technology*, **62**: 255–263.
3. Carlsson, L. A., Aronsson, C.-G., Backlund, J. (1989). Notch Sensitivity of Thermoset and Thermoplastic Laminates Loaded in Tension, *Journal of Materials Science*, **24**: 1670-1682.
4. Eriksson, I. and Aronsson, C.G. (1990). Strength of Tensile Loaded Graphite/Epoxy Laminates Containing Cracks, Open and Filled Holes, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **24**(5):456–482.
5. Kortschot, M.T. and Beaumont, P.W.R. (1990). Damage Mechanics of Composite Materials: I – Measurements of Damage and Strength, *Composites Science and Technology*, **39**:289–301.
6. Hallett, S. R. and Wisnom, M. R. (2006). Experimental Investigation of Progressive Damage and the Effect of Layup in Notched Tensile Tests, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **40**(2):119-141.
7. de Morais, A. B. (2000). Open-hole Strength of Quasi-Isotropic Laminates, *Composites Science and Technology*, **60**:1997–2004.

8. Pinnell M.F. (1996). An Examination of the Effect of Composite Constituent Properties on the Notched Strength Performance of Composite Materials, *Composites Science and Technology*, **56**:1405–1413.
9. Wang, J., Callus, P.J., Bannister, M.K. (2004). Experimental and Numerical Investigation of the Tension and Compression Strength of Un-notched and Notched Quasi-Isotropic Laminates, *Composite Structures*, **64**:297–306.
10. O’Higgins, R.M., McCarthy, M.A., McCarthy, C.T. (2008). Comparison of Open Hole Tension Characteristics of High Strength Glass and Carbon Fibre-Reinforced Composite Materials, *Composites Science and Technology*, **68**:2770–2778.
11. O’Higgins, R.M., Padhi, G.S., McCarthy, M.A., McCarthy, C.T. (2004). Experimental and Numerical Study of the Open-Hole Tensile Strength of Carbon/Epoxy Composites, *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, **40**(4):269–278.
12. Soutis, C. and Lee, J. (2008). Scaling Effects in Notched Carbon Fibre/Epoxy Composites Loaded in Compression, *Journal of Materials Science*, **43**:6593–6598.
13. Soutis, C., Fleck, N.A. and Smith, P.A. (1991). Compression Fatigue Behaviour of Notched Carbon Fibre-Epoxy Laminates, *International Journal of Fatigue*, **13**(4):303-312.
14. Lee, J. and Soutis, C. (2008). Measuring the Notched Compressive Strength of Composite Laminates: Specimen Size Effects, *Composites Science and Technology*, **68**:2359–2366.
15. Green, B.G., Wisnom, M.R., Hallet, S.R. (2007). An Experimental Investigation Into the Tensile Strength Scaling of Notched Composites, *Composites: Part A*, **38**:867–878.
16. ASTM Standard D 5766/D 5766M – 02 (2002). Standard Test Method for Open Hole Tensile Strength of Polymer Matrix Composite Laminates, *Annual book of ASTM standards*, 15.03.
17. ASTM Standard D 6484/D 6484M – 04 (2004). Standard Test Method for Open Hole Compressive Strength of Polymer Matrix Composite Laminates, *Annual book of ASTM standards*, 15.03.
18. ASTM Standard D 6742/D 6742M – 02 (2002). Standard Practice for Filled-Hole Tension and Compression Testing of Polymer Matrix Composite Laminates, *Annual book of ASTM standards*, 15.03.
19. AITM (Airbus Industrie Test Method) 1-0007 (2001). Fibre Reinforced Plastics: Determination of Notched, Unnotched and Filled Hole Tensile Strength, *Airbus Industrie Test Method*.
20. Tsai, S. W., *Strength & Life of Composites*, Composites Design Group, 2008.
21. Ha S. K., Jin K. K., and Huang Y., “Micro-Mechanics of Failure (MMF) for Continuous Fiber Reinforced Composites”, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **42**: 1873 - 1895, 2008.